

Perspectives of Electrification in Uzbekistan: Engineering View

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ABSTRACT:

Nowadays, electrification is actively developing in the Middle East, especially in Uzbekistan. The particular reason for that is air pollution, which urges government to deal with this problem. The research materials are documents and articles describing the development strategy of Uzbekistan. Since the experience and functionality is studied, the results might be of interest to both practitioners and policy theorists striving to develop this field and ensure the use of modern technologies to reduce the level of air pollution in the region. In the following article, information is going to be analyzed and summarized to provide strategies from engineering perspectives.

The review of the relevant literature examines and theoretically analyzes the changes and historic background, including current problems and solutions in the electricity sector and results. Scientific analysis of the literature provides an opportunity to develop measures to improve efficiency in this area.

The methodology section shows the methods used in the research and the ways to overcome the existing problems and shortcomings in the electricity sector, including recommendations that need to be implemented to improve management efficiency.

The conclusion shows the ways to overcome the existing problems and shortcomings in the electricity sector, the potential for the development of the electricity sector to improve the efficiency of energy field and reduce pollution in the region.

Keywords: electricity, electrification of Uzbekistan, energy industry, renewable energy sources, air pollution, emission, ecology.

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INTRODUCTION

In many regions around the globe, electricity generation still relies heavily on fossil fuels, which carry a number of risks due to their exhaustible and environmentally polluting nature [13]. However, many areas are endowed with significant renewable energy sources (RES), such as solar, wind, biomass, geothermal, and hydro. Due to their industrial and population growth, developing countries face rapidly rising electricity demand. This demand can stimulate RES development, contribute to improving the wellbeing of the population, improve energy accessibility and security, and promote social and economic development around the world [14-17].

The nature of the electricity grid is changing drastically, as are our nation's environmental goals, so our policy thinking needs to change profoundly, too. Mounting research suggests that aggressive electrification of energy end uses – such as space heating, water heating, and transportation – is needed if the Uzbekistan and the world are to achieve ambitious emission reduction goals for carbon dioxide. This concept, the electrification of energy end uses that have been powered by fossil fuels (natural gas, propane, gasoline, diesel, or fuel oil) in order to reduce greenhouse gas emissions, is called “environmentally beneficial electrification.” Achieving the greenhouse gas emissions reductions possible through environmentally beneficial electrification will require routinely revisiting

and updating prevailing energy efficiency metrics and accounting methodologies in order to maximize gains. Specifically, it is timely to consider whether reduced electricity consumption (i.e., kWh) is the optimal compass with which to navigate the path to a low-carbon future when, in fact, substitution of electricity for fossil fuels may in some cases increase electricity consumption [18].

According to the opinion of the researcher Saidov, the energy market of Uzbekistan, as in many countries, is the largest network of natural monopolies (pipeline transportation of oil, oil products and gas; production and transportation of electricity and heat). Production processes in the energy sector are characterized by strong negative externalities, which are reflected in the environmental damage caused by fuel and energy companies. All this determines the need for government control of the fuel and energy sector [22].

Improving efficiency through the modernization of existing technologies in the electricity generation network, attracting local and foreign investment in the network, the introduction of modern management mechanisms in the production, transmission and distribution of electricity is one of the current issues.

The world history of energy was developed unfortunately in such a way that people, after having exhausted wood stocks, discovered more high-calorie kinds of fuel as coal, oil and natural gas, and staked on them. In other words, they staked on fuel reserves in the interior of the Earth. But, on the one hand, the reserves of oil, gas, coal are not at all endless. To compose all these reserves, nature has needed millions of years, but they will be utilized within hundreds of years. At a modern level of energy resources consumption, oil will last 50 years, natural gas – 73 years, coal – 170 years, brown coal – 500 years.

Today people in the world have begun to think more seriously about how to prevent injurious plunder of the Earth riches. We know that the reserves of fuel will last for many centuries if only people act in such a way [21].

How should the situation be changed? How should constantly growing needs in energy be adjusted with environment protection concern? How can we minimize the negative impact of producing and utilization of energy for people's needs on the environment? The progressive mankind has found the answer to these questions in utilization of renewable sources of energy (RSE).

They are:

- a. solar energy;
- b. wind power;
- c. energy of the small springs and currents;
- d. geothermal energy;
- e. biomass (household, agricultural wastes, wastes of live-stock breeding, poultry farming, wood, wood processing industry, etc.);
- f. low-potential heat (diffused heat of air, ocean water, seas and reservoirs)

The introductory part of this article highlights the existing problems in the electricity sector, not only in Uzbekistan, but in the whole world.

The review of the relevant literature examines and theoretically analyzes the changes and historic background, including current problems and solutions in the electricity sector and results. Scientific analysis of the literature provides an opportunity to develop measures to improve efficiency in this area.

The methodology section shows the methods used in the research and the ways to overcome the existing problems and shortcomings in the electricity sector, including recommendations that need to be implemented to improve management efficiency.

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LITERATURE REVIEW

The development of the electrical industry goes back to the Soviet Union and different states of Central Asia, including The State of Uzbekistan (USSR). Soviet and Uzbek scientists were working hand in hand to develop this industry on the land of Uzbekistan. The following works and articles show us the progress of electrification in Soviet times.

Training of technical specialists in the Turkestan region, work carried out in this regard at people (later Central Asian State) University was observed in works published in different years by G.N. Cherdantsev, G.I. Zheltova, Yu.V. Steklov [1-4].

In the work published under the general editorship of P.S. Neporojnyi, the measures taken regarding electrification in the former Soviet Union republics were analyzed [5]. Economic processes are partly reflected in the work devoted to the national policy of the Soviets in Central Asia, and information is also given about the Bozsuv hydroelectric power station [6]. Construction work is organized by manual labor. It is interesting to say that the entire mechanized equipment consisted only of railway wagons, pumping equipment, and a diesel-powered concrete mixer. Despite this, Bozsuv hydroelectric power station will be completed in a short time. The dam was built in 94 days, and the hydroelectric power station building and the main part of the hydrostructure were built in 9 months.

In M. Nekrasova's article, the main focus is on the issue of electrification in the country in Soviet historiography of the 20th century. The author thoroughly analyzes the main scientific works published in connection with the completion of the GOERO plan in 1931–1935 until the beginning of the 70s, in which the problem of electrification by historians, energy and economists emphasizes that joint work on it is the guarantee of its successful learning [7].

In M. Matniyazov's work on the issues of the development and location of the republic's industry, the development of electrification in Uzbekistan during 1924–1974 was considered from the perspective of the ideology of the time and "socialist industrialization", while in another work, electrification and its social consequences were studied on the basis of materials related to Central Asian republics [8].

In S.I. Babakhanova's work on the industry of Samarkand, it is shown that the city's need for electricity can be fully satisfied by heat and, especially, hydropower plants built on the Zarafshan River [9].

In monograph by M. Babakhanov, the industry of Turkestan and the conditions of its workers are analyzed on the basis of rich factual materials, and it is noted that the share of industry in the national economy is insignificant, technical progress has stopped, despite the presence of rich hydropower reserves of the country, there is not a single such power plant [12].

Sustainable development of agriculture and the related light and food industry in Uzbekistan is largely related to the processes of rational use of available natural resources, in particular, water and land resources. The geographic location of our republic (location inside the continent) and the extreme continentality of the climate (many sunny days), low rainfall, high evaporation requires effective use of available water resources. It is known that for this reason, the agricultural sector of the republic's agriculture is organized on the basis of the construction of hydro technical structures based on irrigated agriculture and the effective use of their technical and economic potential. The construction of hydro technical structures and their use in land irrigation in our republic dates back to ancient times. According to historical data, small reservoirs - ponds were built in the territory of the Central Asian countries at the end of the old era and the beginning of the new era. The purpose of their construction was to collect water from small streams and then use it for irrigation.

METHODOLOGY

The methods of studying existing scientific research articles on the electricity sector development in Uzbekistan, study of statistical data and economic comparison and analysis, data grouping, are widely used.

DISCUSSION

Electricity generation is the burning of certain types of energy (coal, fuel, gas), the conversion of nuclear energy and kinetic energy (water, etc.) into electrical energy. This can cause environmental disasters, such as acid rains, air pollution and global warming.

Since the beginning of independence, the Government of Uzbekistan has implemented its energy policy as part of its socio-economic policy, focusing it largely on maintaining Uzbekistan's energy security and using energy resources to further the social aims of the society of Uzbekistan. The current energy policy and reforms in the Republic of Uzbekistan are conditionally divided into 4:

I - the period of formation of energy independence (1990-2000);

II - the period of the first reforms (2001-2016);

III - the period of radical change (2017-2019);

IV - New Uzbekistan energy (2020 - n).

Historically, first, "Uzbekenergo" and "Uzbekgidroenergostroy" have been working to establish an effective management system for enterprises and organizations in the energy and electrification sectors located in Uzbekistan, to improve their structures, to meet the needs of the economy in electricity and heat in the transition to market relations. The Ministry of Energy and Electrification of the Republic of Uzbekistan was established on the basis of the Construction and Assembly Trust and their existing structural subdivisions. Nowadays, The Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan approved the "Concept Note for ensuring electricity supply in Uzbekistan in 2020-2030" [10]

This Concept Note on the provision of electricity in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2020-2030 was developed with a view to satisfy growing demand in the Republic of Uzbekistan and ensuring further balanced development power sector based on international best practices and modern trends in the development of electricity industries globally. Also in the period 2020-2030, special attention will be paid to the development of renewable energy generation, especially solar energy.

To achieve the development indicators of renewable energy, the target parameters of the annually commissioned capacities of renewable energy facilities in 2020-2030 have been determined, providing for the construction of 3 GW of wind and 5 GW of solar power plants.

It is planned to carry out work on 62 projects, including the construction of 35 hydroelectric power stations with a total capacity of 1,537 MW and the modernization of 27 existing hydroelectric power stations with an increase of capacity by 186 MW. As a result, by 2030 the total capacity of the hydroelectric power station will be 3,785 MW, the volume of generated electric energy - 13.1 billion kWh (2.2 times by 2019) [20].

By studying examples from other countries, like USA we can come to the following results: Firstly, success of the adoption and implementation of public policy goals to achieve GHG emissions reductions in USA shows us that in 2009, the U.S. established a national goal to reduce overall GHG emissions approximately 17% below 2005 levels by 2020. Minnesota and California, for example, have set an 80% GHG reduction goal by 2050.

The nine states comprising the Regional Greenhouse Gas Initiative (RGGI) originally imposed a cap on GHG emissions from their electric generation units in January 2009, then further reduced that cap from 165 million short tons to 91 million tons in 2014 with an additional 2.5% annual reduction until 2020. These targets have significantly impacted the Northeast electricity grid, producing a lasting impact on that region's GHG emissions profile [18].

In 2018, Uzbekistan ratified the Paris Agreement and adopted a national commitment to reduce GHG emissions per unit of GDP by 10% of the 2010 level by 2030. According to the Strategy on the Transition of the Republic of Uzbekistan to the "Green" Economy for the Period 2019-2030, Uzbekistan aims to increase the share of RESs in total electricity generation to more than 25% by 2030. It also plans to double its energy efficiency indicator, reduce the carbon intensity of GDP, and provide the entire population and all economic sectors with access to modern, inexpensive and reliable energy.

Ongoing global warming trends pose a great risk to human health and economic development, and Uzbekistan is among the countries most vulnerable to climate change. Ratification of the Paris Agreement imposes certain obligations on the country, such as reducing GHG emissions and attracting additional funds to modernize and improve energy efficiency.

Uzbekistan's greatest GHG emissions (more than 80%) originate in the energy sector, from the combustion of fossil fuels (oil, natural gas and coal) and technological methane leaks during the extraction, processing and transportation of natural gas. The share of emissions from fuel combustion has fallen from 71% to 59% in recent years, while at the same time the share of methane leaks from oil and gas complexes and coal production has risen. The increase in emissions associated with methane leaks is mainly due to higher volumes of gas processing (including transit gas) [11].

The following trend shows us that the government of Uzbekistan is really solving the issue with emission, decreasing amount of pollution shows that Uzbekistan can reduce expected levels of emission till 2030 as planned in Paris Agreement.

CONCLUSION

Uzbekistan's power region development is crucial for the whole Central Asia, boosting industrial increase and decreasing nearby air pollution. Research from the early 20th century to the 1990s often overlooked broader modifications, socio-monetary factors, and superior overseas practices, focusing as a substitute on electrification as part of socialist development. Significant development has been made in reducing greenhouse gas emissions, but extra can be carried out by using green electricity technology and selling their use, which might shop energy and decrease fossil fuel dependence. Today, Uzbekistan ranks 50th out of 215 nations in electrification development.

It should be underlined that there are very optimistic prognoses concerning the utilization of renewable energy resources in the Central Asia as well as in the other parts of the world. It is promoting the solving of three global problems mankind is facing today – energy safety, environment protection and food safety.

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